

Photocatalysis : A frontier of photochemistry

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Photocatalysis is an emerging area of photochemistry, which includes photocatalytic oxidation, reduction, degradation, etc. Various photocatalytic pathways have been discussed along with some synthetic, environmental and biological applications.

Photochemistry is concerned with reactions, which are initiated by electronically excited molecules generated by absorption of suitable radiations in visible or near ultraviolet region. Chemical reactions in presence of semiconducting materials and light are known as photocatalytic reactions. Semiconductors with suitable band gaps can act as quantum collectors. On irradiating the material with desired energy (greater than the band gap of semiconductor) can cause a number of photocatalytic reactions. Commonly used semiconductors are binary chalcogenides of various metals like Cd, Fe, Zr, Mo, Zn, etc., but the most commonly used semiconductors are oxides of zinc and titanium and sulphides of cadmium and zinc.

Photocatalytic reactions are broadly classified as (i) homogeneous photocatalysis, in which photocatalyst (semiconductor) and substrate exist in same phase and (ii) heterogeneous photocatalysis, where photocatalyst and the substrate exist in different phases.

Materials can be categorised as conductors, insulators and semiconductors. Semiconductors play an important role in many of these reactions. Semiconductors are mainly of two types : (i) n-type and (ii) p-type. The n-type semiconductors are those which exhibit conductivity due to the flow of excess negative electrons while p-type semiconductors exhibit conductivity due to positive holes. The energy gap (band gap) between valence band (highest occupied molecular orbital, HOMO) and conduction band

Fig. 1. Classification of materials.

(lowest unoccupied molecular orbital, LUMO) in a semiconductor is of medium order, and it will behave as a conductor under certain conditions, i.e. on exposure to light, at high temperature, etc. (Fig. 1).

An electron transfer process is involved in a

photocatalytic reaction from semiconductor to substrate or vice-versa. As such, three steps can be envisaged for the final formation of oxidized donor [S⁺] and/or reduced acceptor [S⁻] (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Various possibilities of electron and/or hole transfer : (i) excitation of an electron in conduction band of the semiconductor leaving a (h⁺) hole in its valence band, (ii) transfer of an excited electron from conduction band of the semiconductor to the unfilled energy level of substrate (S) to produce S⁻, (iii) transfer of an electron from the lowest filled energy level of donor substrate (S) to neutralize this hole and to produce S⁺, (iv) involves both processes (ii) and (iii), and (v) neither process (ii) nor (iii) takes place.

The semiconductor is obtained as such at the end of the reaction and hence, it can be concluded that these photocatalytic reactions can be initiated so as to drive the reactions in a particular direction depending on the band gap of the semiconductors. Since many reactions can be driven under favourable condition in the presence of a photocatalyst, it has opened new avenues of research in the field of photocatalytic reactions. Extensive reviews in this field has been made from time to time¹⁻⁸.

Photocatalytic oxidation

The photocatalytic oxidation takes place in absence of molecular oxygen or where oxygen does not participate. In these reactions an electronically excited donor molecule (D) transfers an electron to a suitable acceptor molecule (A), i.e. an oxidizing agent,

Wada *et al.*⁹ observed photooxidation of methane and ethane with oxygen over ZnO and molybdenum-loaded

ZnO as photocatalysts. Larson and Falconer¹⁰ investigated oxidation of trichloroethane in presence of TiO₂ as photocatalyst whereas Blatter and Frei¹¹ reported the photooxidation of small alkanes by O₂ in zeolite as photocatalyst using red light.

Cunningham and Srijarani¹² observed TiO₂ sensitized photodehydrogenation of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde. It involves conversion of the surface hydroxyls to surface bound *OH radicals which either react with adsorbed benzyl alcohol or suffer electron-hole recombination.

Brezova *et al.*¹³ reported ethyl formate and surface formate as the primary products during photocatalytic oxidation of 2-ethoxyethanol in an aqueous suspension of TiO₂. Photocatalytic oxidation of propan-2-ol by zeolite composite and CdS was carried out by Green and Rudham¹⁴. Cao and Suils¹⁵ observed photooxidation of propan-2-ol to acetone using amorphous manganese oxide as catalyst. Photooxidation of thiols in self-assembled monolayers of gold was investigated by Huang and Hemminger¹⁶.

Wei *et al.*¹⁷ reported photocatalytic oxidation of phenol in presence of hydrogen peroxide and titanium dioxide. Saria *et al.*¹⁸ used TiO₂ for the electron spin resonance study of radicals formed during photooxidation of phenol. Similarly kinetics of photocatalytic oxidation of phenol on TiO₂ surface was investigated by Wei and Wan¹⁹. Pelizzetti *et al.*²⁰ studied photocatalytic activity and selectivity of titania colloids on photooxidation of phenol and atrazine. The photocatalyzed oxidation of phenol, 2-chlorophenol and pentachlorophenol coupled with semiconductor combination such as CdS/TiO₂ leads to an increase in the rate of photocatalytic reaction²¹. Somrani *et al.*²² reported photocatalytic oxidation of substituted toluenes with irradiated TiO₂ semiconductor.

Attanasio *et al.*²³ used tungsten isopolyanion as photocatalyst for aerobic photooxidation of substituted benzenes. Methyl viologens has been used by Muzyka and Fox²⁴ as an electron trap in the TiO₂-mediated photocatalysis of Diels-Alder dimerization of 2,4-dimethyl-1,3-pentadiene.

Metal ions like Cu²⁺, Fe³⁺, Ag⁺ and ferrocynaide ions are less effective as electron trap for this conversion. Recently Parakh *et al.*²⁵ reported photocatalytic oxidation of sulphite to sulphate ions over CdS.

Trillas *et al.*²⁶ reported photooxidation of phenoxycetic acid by illuminated TiO₂ catalyst. Zhao *et al.*²⁷ investigated photooxidation of surfactants using TiO₂. The use of zirconium and germanium phosphates in heterogeneous photocatalytic oxidation of naphthalenes to

phthalic anhydride was reported by Monaci and Ginestra²⁸. Singhal *et al.*²⁹ observed the photocatalytic degradation of cetylpyridinium chloride over aqueous TiO₂ suspension,

Photocatalytic conversion of OCN⁻ to CO₃²⁻ over TiO₂ was studied by Peral *et al.*³⁰,

Pollema *et al.*³¹ investigated photocatalytic oxidation of cyanide to nitrate over TiO₂ particles. In this photocatalytic oxidation, cyanide is first oxidized to cyanate, then photocatalytically oxidized via nitrite all the way to nitrate,

This conversion is useful in pollution control since nitrate is less hazardous contaminant as compared to cyanide ions.

Photocatalytic reduction

The photocatalytic reduction of methyl yellow by CdS nanoparticles mediated in reverse micelles was studied by Zhang and Shen³². Sviridov and Kulak³³ reported mechanism of photoreduction of silver on tungsten trioxide. Photoreduction of iron(III) in marine mineral aerosol was studied by Zhu *et al.*³⁴. Generation of homogeneous rhodium particles by photoreduction of rhodium(III) on TiO₂ colloids grafted on SiO₂ was reported by Fernandez *et al.*³⁵. Photocatalytic reduction of copper(II) on ZnO was observed by Dangi *et al.*³⁶. Photoreduction of [PtCl₆]²⁻ on CdS was investigated by Li *et al.*³⁷. Lin *et al.*³⁸ observed photocatalytic reduction and immobilization of hexavalent chromium on TiO₂ in aqueous basic media. Soria *et al.*³⁹ studied dinitrogen photoreduction of ammonia over TiO₂ powder doped with ferric ions.

The efficiency of the photoreduction of iron(III) complexes with kojic acid derivatives was evaluated by Sima *et al.*⁴⁰. Tennakone *et al.*⁴¹ reported photoreduction of nitrogen to ammonia by vanadium(III) substituted hydrous ferric oxide. This system gives significant yield of ammonia because photogenerated holes are efficiently scavenged by V³⁺,

Taqui Khan *et al.*⁴² studied such a photocatalytic reduction using ruthenium(III)-(ethylenediaminetetraacetate-2,2'-bipyridyl) complex as a sensitizer in Pt-TiO₂ semiconductor particulate system.

Photocatalytic reduction of nitrate ions into nitrite and ammonia was observed by Kudo *et al.*⁴³. Photocatalytic reduction of nitrite and nitrate on ZnS and oxide (ZnO, ZrO₂, Fe₂O₃, etc.) was carried out by Ranjit *et al.*⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. Anpo and Chiba⁴⁷ reported photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ on anchored TiO₂ catalysts. The photocatalyzed reduction of CO₂ in aqueous TiO₂ suspension mixed with copper indicates that free copper metal is required for this reduction in which copper acts as a source of electron⁴⁸. Photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to methane and CH₃COOH by an aqueous suspension of metal-deposited TiO₂ was carried out by Ishitani *et al.*⁴⁹. Sharma *et al.*^{50,51} reported photocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide using dye coated TiO₂,

Photoreduction of CO₂ to CO catalyzed by colloidal CdS and ZnS was observed by Kanemoto *et al.*^{52,53}. Kanemoto *et al.*⁵⁴ also reported CdS-catalyzed photoreduction of CO₂. Sayama and Arakawa⁵⁵ investigated photocatalytic decomposition of water and photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ over ZrO₂ catalyst. Eggine *et al.*⁵⁶ studied photoreduction of CO₂ on ZnS to give 2-carbon and 4-carbon acids. Malati *et al.*⁵⁷ used photocatalysis for the reduction of aqueous carbonate and Cr^{VI}. Photocatalytic reduction of pollutants like Hg^{II} on ZnO-WO₃ dispersion was reported by Wang and Zhuang⁵⁸. This reaction follows first order kinetics and 99.1% of the Hg^{II} can be photoreduced from a solution of 100 µg dm⁻³ concentration under sunlight irradiation for 110 min. Wang *et al.*⁵⁹ observed photocatalytic reduction of environmental pollutants Cr^{VI} over CdS powder under visible light.

Photocatalytic degradation

Photodegradation of dichloromethane, tetrachloroethylene and 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane in aqueous suspension of TiO₂ with natural concentrated and simulated sunlight was investigated by Halmann *et al.*⁶⁰. Martin *et al.*⁶¹ carried out photocatalytic decomposition of chloroform in fully irradiated photoreactor using titanium dioxide particulate suspensions. Yamazaki-Nishida *et al.*⁶² studied photocatalytic degradation of trichloroethylene in the gas phase using TiO₂ pellets. Minero *et al.*⁶³ observed photodegradation of fluorinated aromatics over titania in aqueous media. Brezova *et al.*⁶⁴ studied photocatalytic degradation of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in aqueous system containing powdered and immobilized TiO₂, and *p*-cresol was identified as the main intermediate.

Degradation of ethyl benzene in TiO₂ aqueous suspension was observed by Vidal *et al.*⁶⁵. This photodegradation follows first order kinetics in a concentration range 3–50 µM. 4-Ethylphenol, acetophenone, 2-ethoxyphenol, 3-

ethylphenol and 2-methylbenzyl alcohol were identified as the intermediates. Uchida *et al.*⁶⁶ carried out photocatalytic decomposition of trichlorobenzene using TiO₂ supported on nickel poly(tetrafluoroethylene) composite plate. Photocatalytic degradation of sulfonated aromatics in aqueous TiO₂ suspensions was observed by Sangchakr *et al.*⁶⁷. Somrani *et al.*⁶⁸ investigated photocatalytic degradation of hydroxylated biphenyl compounds. Influence of H₂O₂ on photocatalytic degradation of trinitrotoluene and trinitrobenzene was reported by Dillert *et al.*⁶⁹.

Sclafani *et al.*⁷⁰ studied photocatalytic degradation of phenol in aqueous polycrystalline TiO₂ dispersion. The influence of Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺ and Ag⁺ ions on this reaction was observed. These ions react very easily with peroxo species produced on the catalyst surface and/or in the solution, e.g.

Experimental conditions for the continuous photoproduction of Fenton's reagent (Fe²⁺ + H₂O₂) are achieved in this way. Photodegradation of 4-chlorophenol in water sensitized by semiconductor was reported by Al-Sayyed *et al.*⁷¹,

D'Oliveira *et al.*⁷² reported the photodegradation of dichlorophenol and trichlorophenol in TiO₂ aqueous suspensions. The aromatic intermediate corresponded to the hydroxylation of the aromatic nucleus with the following order of reactivity: *para* > *ortho* >> *meta*. The release of chloride and the evolution of CO₂ also followed pseudo-first order kinetics. Agugugliaro *et al.*⁷³ reported photocatalytic degradation of nitrophenol in aqueous titanium dioxide dispersion, whereas Maillarddupuy *et al.*⁷⁴ carried out degradation of nitrobenzene in water using TiO₂ as photocatalyst.

Photocatalytic dehydrogenation of alcohol in the presence of Pt-CdS was reported by Jin *et al.*⁷⁵. Mansilla and Villasnov⁷⁶ investigated ZnO-catalyzed photodegradation of Kraft-Black liquor, which is an effluent from pulp and paper industry. Platinum-impregnated ZnO yielded 100% discoloration after 60 min (190 kJ m⁻²) of ultraviolet radiations. Sabate *et al.*⁷⁷ studied the kinetics of photocatalytic degradation of 3-chlorosalicylic acid over TiO₂ membranes supported on glass, while photodegradation of substituted benzoic acid on TiO₂ was carried out by Cunningham and Al-Sayyed⁷⁸.

Maillard *et al.*⁷⁹ investigated photodegradation of benzamide in TiO₂ aqueous suspensions, while photodegradation of polyimides was carried out by Hoyle and Anzures⁸⁰. Photocatalytic degradation of polyethylene film by incorporated extra-fine particles of TiO₂ was reported by Ohtani *et al.*⁸¹. Kaczmarek⁸² reported mechanism of photoinitiated degradation of polyethylene oxide by copper complexes in acetonitrile.

Photodegradation of methylene blue using solar light and TiO_2 as semiconductor was investigated by Nogueira and Jardim⁸³ and Lakshmi *et al.*⁸⁴. Recently, photocatalytic degradation of xylydine ponceau and orange-G has been observed by Sharma *et al.*^{85,86} and photocatalytic bleaching of crystal violet by Rao *et al.*⁸⁷.

Muszkat *et al.*⁸⁸ reported solar degradation of xenobiotic contaminants in polluted well water whereas photocatalytic degradation of waste water pollutants was observed by Muneer *et al.*⁸⁹. Rufus *et al.*⁹⁰ observed the decomposition of aqueous sulphide in presence of CdS with iridium sulphide and platinum sulphide as photocatalysts. Hidaka *et al.*⁹¹ investigated the photocatalytic degradation of cyanide in aqueous TiO_2 suspension in aerated conditions. Formation of intermediate OCN^- and its ultimate mineralization to CO_2 and N_2 has been reported,

Sayama and Arakawa⁹² investigated photocatalytic decomposition of liquid water over various semiconductor catalysts. Zhao *et al.*^{93,94} carried out photodegradation of some surfactants. Photocatalytic degradation of mixed surfactants and some commercial soap detergent products using suspended TiO_2 catalysts was observed by Rao and Dube⁹⁶.

Photocatalytic activity

The effect of oxygen on photocatalytic reaction of ethanol over some titanium dioxide photocatalysts was observed by Iseda *et al.*^{97,98}. Photocatalytic reaction of ethambutol on zinc oxide powder was observed by Lodha *et al.*⁹⁹. Kais *et al.*¹⁰⁰ studied photocatalytic reaction of acetic acid on platinum loaded TiO_2 . Photocatalysis of benzophenone catalyzed by colloidal CdS microcrystallites was performed by Kanemoto *et al.*¹⁰¹. Adsorption properties of TiO_2 related to the photocatalytic degradation of organic contaminants in water was reported by Chen *et al.*¹⁰². Kerzhentser *et al.*¹⁰³ observed photocatalytic removal of pollutant in water at room temperature.

Yanagida¹⁰⁴ reported photocatalytic hydrogen evolution on zinc sulphide dispersion. Mills *et al.*¹⁰⁵ carried out water purification by semiconductor photocatalysis. Hydrogen production from water and conversion of CO_2 to useful chemicals were studied by Ichikawa and Doi¹⁰⁶. Kobayakawa *et al.*¹⁰⁷ observed enhancement of the photocatalytic activity of CdS powder by heat treatment with KCl and KBr, while photocatalysis on native and platinum loaded TiO_2 and ZnO catalysts was studied by Anpo *et al.*¹⁰⁸.

Sakata *et al.*¹⁰⁹ reported photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 with cerium oxide. Gao *et al.*¹¹⁰ improved the photocatalytic activity of titanium(IV) oxide by dispersion of Au on TiO_2 . Lee *et al.*^{111,112} reported enhancement of photocatalytic activity of titanium(IV) oxide with molyb-

denum(IV) oxide and effect of silver. Papp *et al.*^{113,114} reported photocatalytic activity of titanium(IV) oxide with palladium and surface acidity of TiO_2 , WO_3/TiO_2 and $\text{MoO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ photocatalysts, whereas Tada and Honda¹¹⁵ observed photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 film coated on internal light guide. Efficient TiO_2 powder and film photocatalysis with rutile crystal structure was carried out by Sopayan *et al.*¹¹⁶. Zhang *et al.*¹¹⁷ studied photocatalytic property of titanium silicate zeolite.

Miscellaneous photocatalytic reactions

Photopolymerization of vinyl ether by hydroxy and methyl thioallyl phosphonium salts as photocatalytic initiators was observed by Komoto *et al.*¹¹⁸. Davidson *et al.*¹¹⁹ studied photobleaching and photoyellowing of paper containing lignin, while simultaneous observation of photobleaching and photorefractive effects in germanium doped fibres was observed by Kanellopoulos *et al.*¹²⁰. Photodarkening and photobleaching of CdS microclusters grown in zeolites were studied by Moyo *et al.*¹²¹.

Photocatalytic isomerization, hydrogenation and decomposition reactions of alkenes over TiO_2 adsorbed water were studied by Kodama and Yagi¹²². Shiragami *et al.*¹²³ observed photocatalytic *cis-trans* isomerization of electron-deficient alkenes in presence of CdS powder. The photocatalytic isomerization of 2-butene on ZrO_2 catalyst was reported by Moon *et al.*¹²⁴ and Takahashi *et al.*¹²⁵ reported photoconductivity of ultrathin zinc oxide films.

Photomineralization of 4-chlorophenol sensitized by TiO_2 was reported by Mills and Morris¹²⁶. Photochemical mineralization of paraquinol dissolved in water by TiO_2 supported on polythene and polypropylene films, was observed by Tennakone and Kottegoda¹²⁷, while Terzian and Serpone¹²⁸ reported mineralization of xylenols by illuminated TiO_2 in oxygenated aqueous media.

Applications

Photocatalysis has opened many avenues of further researches as far as its application part is concerned. The photocatalysis has emerged as a probable solution to some of the problems like energy crisis, environmental pollution, wastewater treatment etc. Semiconductor particulate system can provide a low cost and convenient way of treating several undesirable chemicals. The principle of such a treatment lies in initiating an oxidation or reduction process at the semiconductor surface. For example H_2S , which is a by-product in the coal and petroleum industry, can be oxidized to sulphur at CdS semiconductor surface¹²⁹. A quantum yield of 50% has been reported for the reaction between sulphide anion and photogenerated valence band holes in CdS suspensions. Similarly, photocatalytic transformation of CN^- to SCN^- has been carried out in presence of rhodium-loaded CdS particulate system¹³⁰.

Photocatalysis can be used to eliminate pollutants from the environment. Chloral hydrate is a toxic compound, which is used for the synthesis of insecticides. Tanaka *et al.*¹³¹ reported the photocatalytic degradation of chloral

hydrate in aqueous semiconductor suspension via the formation of $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals and utilizing these $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals for oxidizing chloral hydrate,

Photocatalysis has been used for the degradation of pesticides like atrazine¹³² and also as a bactericide for spectrococci¹³³. Nehara *et al.*¹³⁴ made use of irradiated titania semiconductor photocatalyst slurries in aqueous media for photooxidative degradation of the pesticide permethrin.

It has been shown by Andres and Domenech¹³⁵ that in the presence of ZnO, Hg^{II} can be photocatalytically eliminated from aqueous solutions. Munner *et al.*¹³⁶ investigated the photocatalytic degradation of an industrial pollutant like methyl vinyl ketone in aqueous solution using suspended TiO₂ and TiO₂-immobilized on glass surface. The two oxidizing species $\cdot\text{OH}$ and O₂ are the primary species utilized in photocatalytic degradation process. These oxidation reaction resulted in the depletion of O₂ and methyl vinyl ketone and in the formation of CO₂ and other semioxidized products in solution,

Herrmann *et al.*¹³⁷ reported heterogeneous photocatalysis as an emerging technology for waste water treatment. It may also prove useful in recovery of some transition metals from industrial effluents. Das *et al.*¹³⁸ observed photocatalytic degradation of waste water pollutants involving TiO₂ mediated oxidation of some polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons. Recently Osawa and Sunakani¹³⁹ reported photodegradation of polyurethane and polyvinyl chloride. Ahmed and Attia¹⁴⁰ used certain aerogel materials for photocatalytic detoxification of cyanide in waste waters. Recently, Osunda and Huntsman¹⁴¹ have investigated photoreduction of manganese oxides in sea water. The photocatalysis can also prove to be useful in recovery of some costly metals from aqueous solutions, even if present in traces. Photocatalytic deposition of silver on TiO₂ powder was reported by Herrmann *et al.*¹³⁷.

It has been advocated and predicted that hydrogen will be the fuel of future and any newer method for efficient photocatalytic production of H₂ will be a welcome addition in solving the existing problem of energy crisis. The field of heterogeneous photocatalysis has already grown out of its infancy and has now emerged as a major field of research. The recent developments of ultrafine semiconductor particles has added some newer dimensions. The ability of such semiconductors to carry out redox processes with greater efficiency and selectivity than in the homogeneous solutions has made them more important in the conversion and storage of solar energy, in the mineralization of chemical pollutants and also for the treatment of some dreadful diseases.

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